

Additional file 5: Detailed results related to Figure 1 – Results of logistic regression model (odds ratios and standard errors)

	<i>Specialist use</i>	<i>GP use</i>	<i>Specialist unmet needs</i>	<i>GP unmet needs</i>	<i>Emergency dept. use</i>	<i>Avoidable hospitalization</i>
<i>HV (ref. regular access)</i>	0.466*** (0.0937)	0.571** (0.145)	1.095 (0.256)	0.915 (0.214)	0.761 (0.152)	0.996 (0.230)
<i>EHC (ref. regular access)</i>	0.899 (0.279)	0.814 (0.339)	2.119*** (0.496)	1.050 (0.304)	1.034 (0.330)	1.514 (0.465)
<i>Age</i>	1.015* (0.00852)	1.028*** (0.0101)	1.018* (0.00896)	1.012 (0.00948)	0.995 (0.00918)	1.015 (0.00965)
<i>Male (ref. female)</i>	1.507** (0.270)	1.719*** (0.334)	1.106 (0.207)	1.106 (0.218)	2.319*** (0.419)	1.145 (0.254)
<i>Constant</i>	0.466*** (0.0937)	0.571** (0.145)	1.095 (0.256)	0.915 (0.214)	0.761 (0.152)	0.996 (0.230)
<i>Observations</i>	863	863	863	863	863	863
<i>p-value (F-test)</i>	0.990	0.708	0.567	0.945	0.083	0.191

Standard errors in parentheses; *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$